

Instruments of Fiscal Policy and Financial Deepening in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated effect of fiscal policy instruments on financial deepening in Nigeria. Following extensive theoretical and empirical literature, the study employed the Ordinary Least Square estimation technique (OLS) to capture the objectives of the study. Time series data on financial deepening, capital and recurrent expenditure, government borrowing and tax revenue ranging from 1981 to 2022 were sourced from World Bank Development Indicators (WDI) and was employed in the analysis of the study. Evidence from the estimated OLS model indicated that capital expenditure had a negative and significant effect on financial deepening in Nigeria; recurrent expenditure had a positive and insignificant relationship with financial deepening in Nigeria; government borrowing had a positive and significant relationship with financial deepening in Nigeria; taxation revenue had a negative and insignificant relationship with financial deepening in Nigeria while a long run relationship existed between fiscal policy instruments and financial deepening in Nigeria at 5 percent level of significance. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that to ensure higher productivity of capital in promoting economic growth, capital allocations should be prioritized based on projects and areas that have strong benefits to the citizens and sound linkages with various sectors of the economy.

Keywords: Fiscal Policy; Financial Deepening; Capital Expenditure; Recurrent Expenditure.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiscal policy is the use of government revenues and expenditure policies to regulate and stabilize the economy toward development. The government uses this policy in other to achieve its objectives in stabilizing the economy. This includes the macroeconomic objectives (price stability, economic growth, reduction in poverty, balance of payment equilibrium etc.) and microeconomic influence on efficiency of resources use (Torruam and Chiawa, 2018).

Fiscal policy also is essentially concerned with manipulating the financial operations of government with a view of furthering certain economic policy objective. In the other words, it consists of government decisions to vary certain fiscal aggregate such as total government spending and tax revenues as opposed to some other aspects of public finance which are primarily concerned with the effect of specific government expenditure and taxes (Stein 1968). Fiscal policy is majorly used in terms of government expenditure, tax revenue, government investment, budgeting and debts (Babalola, 2015).

Mukundi (2013) went further to opine that financial deepening (depth) is a concept usually understood to mean three things. First, that sectors and agents are able to and indeed use a range of financial markets for financial saving and investment decisions, including at long maturities. This is the element of degree of access to finance. Secondly, the financial intermediaries and markets are able to and actually deploy larger volumes of capital and larger turnover, without

necessitating large corresponding movements in asset prices. This happens when the market is liquid (Chami, Fullenkamp and Sharma, 2009).

Financial deepening is to improve economic conditions through increased competitive efficiency within financial markets thereby indirectly benefiting non-financial sectors of the economy. Financial deepening also helps in increasing the provision and choices of financial services which would come through its financial infrastructure. Nzotta and Okereke (2019) ascertain that financial deepening is the ability of financial institutions in an economy to effectively mobilize savings for investment purposes. Financial deepening vigorously attracts the reservoir of savings and idle funds and allocates same to entrepreneurs, business, households and government for investments projects and other purposes with a view of returns which forms the basis for economic growth.

The growing importance of stock market and banks around the world has recently opened a new avenue of research into the relationship between fiscal policy instrument and financial deepening (Arestis, Demetriades and Luintel, 2001). The general idea that economic growth is related to financial deepening was first highlighted by Schumpeter in 1911, (Okoli 2010). Financial reforms have been a regular feature of the Nigeria financial system. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has been trying hard to ensure that the financial sector in Nigeria maintain a considerable depth and remain liquid with a view to competing effectively within the global financial market.

The reforms have evolved in response to the challenges posed by developments in the system such as systemic crisis, globalization, technological innovation and financial crisis. The reforms often seek to act proactively to strengthen the system, thus, there is need to deepen the financial sector and reposition it for growth and integration into the global financial system in conformity with international best practice. Based on the forgoing the study investigates, impact of fiscal policy instruments on financial deepening profiling in Nigeria.

The issues of fiscal policy implementation in Nigeria has raised vast number of issues, problems and obstacles to the general growth and development of the economy, as it has been reportedly agreed that, no nation can grow faster than its financial sector. Thus the challenges confronting the sector in the country over the last decades includes; gross mismanagement/ misappropriation of public funds, (Okemini and Uranta, 2008), corruption and ineffective economic policies (Gbosi, 2007); lack of integration of macroeconomic plans and the absence of harmonization and coordination of fiscal policies (Onoh, 2007); inappropriate and ineffective policies (Anyanwu, 2017).

Over the years, government expenditure shows that recurrent expenditure increased from ₦3.819 billion in 1977 to ₦4.805 billion in 1980 and further to ₦36.2196 billion in 1990. Recurrent expenditure was ₦461 billion and ₦1.5893trillion in 2000 and 2007, respectively. It further increased to ₦3.10944 trillion in 2010 and ₦3.6898trillion in 2013 but however declined to ₦2.5303trillion in 2014 (CBN, 2015). Included in its recurrent expenditure other than personnel and various administrative costs are interest payments on debt servicing and other such transfers and extra-budgetary items. The ratio of recurrent expenditure on the overall government expenditure framework in Nigeria's annual budget has always been subjecting of debate in the National Assembly.

The rising profile of Nigeria's indebtedness is a sour point in the public finance management

and speaks volumes of the fiscal discipline of political actor's attitude to the sovereignty of Nigeria. According to Nwankwo (2010), Nigeria debt profile was \$32.5 billion by September 2010, that is, N5, 241,667 million. In year 2000, the total outstanding debt of Nigeria was N3, 995,638 million. These continued to be an upward trend until in 2006 it declined to N3, 177,409 million because of debt cancelation agreement between Nigeria and Paris Club (Okwo, 2010). Thereafter, it started rising again and reached N5, 241,667million.

The Federal government capital expenditure framework has been hinged on administration, economic services, social and community services and transfers (i.e. interest and capital repayment on loans). Due to the pressure from borrowings, transfers were apportioned a larger allocation of capital expenditure on an average of up to 43.83%, social and community services 7.77%, economic services 34.68% and administrative 13.72% from 1986 to 1999 while from 2000 to 2010 transfers took the least with 6.9%, social and community services 13.54%, economic services 50.35% and administrative 29.22% (CBN, 2014).

Imprudent public spending and weak sectorial linkages and other socio- economic maladies constitute the bane of rapid economic growth and development (Amadi, 2016). Also according to Ogbole, (2011) it is evident that one of Nigeria's greatest problems today is the inability to efficiently manage her enormous human and material endowment. During 1981-1999 total capital expenditure amounted to N1694.04billion with an average of 5.33% of total GDP while from 2000-2014 it was averaged at 3.68% with and all time high of 11% in the year 2014 lowest of 1.23% in the year 2012 CBN (2014).

In the year 1993, government expenditure more than doubled and grew by 106% whereas GDP grew at 2%. Interestingly, in the year 2000 government expenditure dropped by 26% whereas GDP grew by 5%. However, by 2013 government expenditure grew by 13% which was accompanied by a growth in GDP by 7%. Over the years (1981-2022), government expenditure has been rising on both recurrent and capital status, despite these vast numerical increases in the figures of the Nations annual budget, the country remains grossly impacted by poverty, financial inequality due to the lack of financial institutions in most remote areas of the country, where basic primary and secondary economic activities that is capable of propelling the national economy to growth and development is located. The study there investigates, impact of fiscal policy instrument on financial deepening profiling in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1.1 Fiscal Policy

The term fiscal policy has conventionally been associated with the use of taxation and public expenditure to influence the level of economic activities. The implementation of fiscal policy is essentially routed through government's budget. It (budget) both reflects and shapes a country's economic life. In fact, the most important aspect of a public budget is its use as a tool in the management of a nation's economy (Omitogun and Ayinla, 2019). Fiscal policy deals with government deliberate actions in spending money and levying taxes with a view to influencing macro-economic variables in a desired direction. This includes sustainable economic growth, high employment creation and low inflation (Microsoft Corporation, 2004). Thus, fiscal policy aims at stabilizing the economy. Increases in government spending or a reduction in taxes tend to pull the economy out of a recession; while reduced spending or increased taxes slow down a boom (Dornbusch and Fischer, 2011).

Fiscal policy involves the use of government spending, taxation and borrowing to influence the pattern of economic activities and also the level and growth of aggregate demand, output and employment. Fiscal policy entails government's management of the economy through the manipulation of its income and spending power to achieve certain desired macroeconomic objectives (goals) amongst which is economic growth (Medee and Nembee, 2011). Olawunmi and Tajudeen (2007) opine that fiscal policy has conventionally been associated with the use of taxation and public expenditure to influence the level of economic activities.

They further said the implementation of fiscal policy is essentially routed through government's budget. Fiscal policy act mostly to achieve macroeconomic policy; it is to reconcile the changes which government modifies in taxation and expenditure, programmes or to regulate the full employment price and total demand to be used through instruments such as government expenditures, taxation and debt management (Hottz-Eakin, Lovely and Tosin, 2009). As noted by Anyanwu (1993), the objective of fiscal policy is to promote economic conditions conducive to business growth while ensuring that any such government actions are consistent with economic stability. From the foregoing, it is clear that if fiscal policy is used with circumspection and synchronized with other measures, it will likely smoothen out business cycles and lead to economic growth and stability.

2.1.2 Tax System

In Nigeria, tax as fiscal policy instrument are used for achieving different objectives such as raising revenue for the government, redistribution of income, efficient allocation of resources (through the provision of social goods and services) encouraging the propensity to save, encouraging investment, stimulate certain sectors of the economy, discouraging the production of certain goods, attracting foreign direct investment etc. The choice and direction of tax policies depend on the intendment of government to influence these competing objectives.

The enactment of the Finance (Miscellaneous Taxation Provisions) Act No.3 of 1993 and decree 104 of 1993 brought major changes in the Nigerian tax system. While Act No.3 of 1993 reviewed the composition of the Federal Board Inland Revenue (FBIR) and also established the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), decree 104 amongst others reviewed the functions of the Joint Tax Board (JTB).

Value added tax (VAT) was introduced through decree No. 102 of 1993 (as amended) but took effect in 1994 to replace Sales tax decree No. 7 of 1986 which hitherto was imposed on all goods manufactured in the country and imported goods. Value added tax is imposed on certain goods and services and charged at the rate of 5% on the value of all taxable goods and services. The decree specified certain goods and services to be exempted for the tax such as all exported goods, medical and pharmaceutical products, products meant for babies, basic food items, commercial vehicles and their spare parts, books and other educational materials, fertilizer, farming machines, agricultural products, farming transportation equipment, veterinary medicines, magazines and newspapers. The services exempted are all services that are exported, medical services, and services that are provided by the community banks, mortgage organizations and the peoples' bank. (Tax laws in Nigeria, 2011).

2.1.3 Financial Deepening

Shaw (1973) defined financial deepening as: „the accumulation of financial assets at a faster pace than the accumulation of non-financial wealth and output“. Levine, (2005) gave a broader definition by explaining that financial deepening occurs when financial markets (primary, secondary and retail), instruments (deposits, loans, foreign exchange, bonds and debt securities) and stakeholders (banks, contractual savings institutions, companies) interact to reduce the costs of contract enforcement, transaction and information in order to perform five main functions namely:

Chiefly among the very benefits of financial deepening in the country is the facilitation of goods and services exchange (e.g. payment services) with in the country. This is aimed at achieving increased economic prosperity and growth over time.

Another outstanding importance of financial deepening is the ability to mobilize and pool savings of a large number of investors. This therefore aids economic progress in the country, through making credit available to the private sector in the country for improved economic activities, which is capable of spurring increased growth and development of the Nigerian economy.

This achievement would also led to the acquisition and processing information about the companies and the potential investment projects and therefore allocating public savings to the most productive uses to diversify and reduce liquidity risk and inter-temporal risk (Levine, 2005; King and Levine, 1993). For the purpose of this study, financial deepening will be defined as the increase in the supply of financial assets in the economy.

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Follow investments and exert corporate governance, and v) diversify and reduce liquidity risk and inter-temporal risk (Levine, 2005; King and Levine, 1993). For the purpose of this study, financial deepening will be defined as the increase in the supply of financial assets in the economy. From the theoretical and empirical review, it is expected positive and significant coefficients of the independent variables leading to an increase in the dependent variable. This means that liquid liabilities, credit to the private sector, commercial-central bank assets and commercial bank deposits when converted into production and sparking market demand act as an incentive to real GDP rise in the country.

2.1.4 Money Supply

In general terms, monetary policy refers to a combination of measures designed to regulate the value, supply and cost of money in an economy, in consonance with the expected level of economic activity (Baghedo and Ebibai, 2014). For most economies, the objects of monetary policy include price stability, maintenance of balance of payments equilibrium, promotion of

employment and output growth, and sustainable development (Folawewo and Osinubi, 2006). These objectives are necessary for the attainment of internal and external balance, and the promotion of long-run economic growth (Imoughele, 2014).

The importance of price stability derives from the harmful effects of price volatility, which undermines the ability of policy makers to achieve other laudable macroeconomic objectives. There is indeed a general consensus that domestic price fluctuation undermines the role of money as a store of value, and frustrates investments and growth (Fischer, 2014). With the achievement of price stability, the conditions in the financial market and institutions would create a high degree of confidence, such that the financial infrastructure of the economy is able to meet the requirements of market participants. Indeed, an unstable or crisis-ridden financial sector will render the transmission mechanism of monetary policy less effective, making the achievement and maintenance of strong macroeconomic fundamental difficult. This is because it is only in a period of price stability that investors and consumers can interpret market signals correctly (Imoughele, 2014).

2.2 Theoretical Literature

2.2.1 Financial Intermediation Theory

The theory of Financial Intermediation advocates that financial intermediaries play a crucial role of intermediation in the growth process by transferring financial resources from the net savers to net borrowers, thus influencing investment and thereby economic growth. The theory suggests that financial intermediaries can overcome a market failure and resolve an information asymmetry problem by transforming the risk characteristics of assets. These asymmetries in credit markets arise because borrowers generally know more about their investment projects than lenders do. Information failures lead to specific forms of transaction costs and financial intermediaries appear to overcome these costs, at least partially. The notion of transaction costs encompasses not only exchange or monetary transaction costs (Tobin, 1963) but also searches, monitoring and auditing costs (Benston and Smith, 1976).

Gurley and Shaw (1960) supported the view that financial intermediaries are an opportunity to enhance borrower's financial capacity in the financial savings and investment process. Thus, the higher the intermediation level in the financial sector, the higher the financial savings mobilized and higher would be investments, which in turn will increase the level of economic growth. In the same way, according to Goldsmith (1969), the financial structure of an economy accelerates economic performance to the extent that it facilitates the migration of funds to the best user, i.e., to the place in the economic system where the funds yield the highest social return". The opinion of Greenwood and Jovanovic (1990) is in line with this view; they argue that financial intermediation promotes growth because it allows a higher rate of return to be earned on capital, and growth in turn provides a means to implement costly financial structures.

2.2.2 Wagner's Law

Wagner's Law is named after the German political economist Adolph Wagner (1835-1917), who developed a "law of increasing state activity" after empirical analysis on Western Europe at the end of the 19th century. He argued that government growth is a function of increased industrialization and economic development.

Wagner stated that during the industrialization process, as the real income per capita of a nation increases, the share of public expenditures in total expenditures increases.

The law cited that “The advent of modern industrial society will result in increasing political pressure for social progress and increased allowance for social consideration by industry.”

Wagner (1893) designed three focal bases for the increased in state expenditure. Firstly, during industrialization process, public sector activity will replace private sector activity. State functions like administrative and protective functions will increase. Secondly, governments needed to provide cultural and welfare services like education, public health, old age pension or retirement insurance, food subsidy, natural disaster aid, environmental protection programs and other welfare functions. Thirdly, increased industrialization will bring out technological change and large firms that tend to monopolize. Governments will have to offset these effects by providing social and merit goods through budgetary means.

2.3 Empirical Literature Review

Ohwofasa, Otefe-Oghara, and Aiyedogbon (2020). The paper assessed the level of development of financial deepening in the banking sector and the extent it has impacted on economic growth over the last two decades. Vector autoregressive (VAR) methodology and its derivatives, impulse response function and variance decomposition, were employed that enable us to scrutinize the relationship between financial deepening and economic growth. The findings show that the series are co-integrated and that long run relationship existed between the variables

Waiyaki (2019), Carried out an assessment of the relationship between financial development, economic growth and poverty in Kenya for the 1997-2012 period. The study attempted to determine the direction of causality between financial development and economic growth as well as the effect of financial development on economic growth with a focus on the banking sector, and the stock market in Kenya. The variables used included broad money supply M3, credit to private sector, bank deposits, stock market capitalization, stock market turnover and volume of stocks traded. The study used OLS method under the PARCH model. The findings show that some financial development variables such as M3 and credit to the private sector did not lead to growth while bank deposits did during the period of the study.

Uddin, Sjö and Shahbaz (2019). Looked at the relationship between financial development and economic growth in Kenya over the period of 1971-2011. The study was based on a Cobb-Douglas production augmented by incorporating financial development. The study established that, in the long run, development of financial sector, (measured by domestic credit provided by banking sector; domestic credit to private sector; money plus quasi money (M2) as a ratio of money (M1) had a positive impact on economic growth.

Onuonga (2019). Examined relationship between economic growth and financial development in Kenya over the period 1980–2011. Financial development was measured by M2 and domestic credit to the private sector. The study used autoregressive distributed lag framework and Granger causality analysis to determine the direction of causality. Findings indicated that there was a stable long-run relationship among, financial development, trade openness and economic growth in Kenya. It also found that financial development had a significant positive effect on economic growth. The interpretation of the findings implied that financial development accelerated and augmented economic growth in Kenya and that economic growth

led to development of the financial sector in Kenya.

Torruam, Chiawa, and Abur (2018). Researched on Financial Deepening and Economic Growth in Nigeria: An Application of Cointegration and Causality Analysis. The study examines the causal relationship between financial deepening and Economic Growth in Nigeria for the period 1990-2011. The stationarity properties of the data and the order of integration of the data were tested using both the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and the Phillip-Perron (PP) test. The variables tested stationary at first differences. The Johansen approach of cointegration was applied to test for the long-run relationship among the variables. The result indicated four (4) cointegrating relations between the variables; the Granger-causality suggests that there is unidirectional causality running from economic growth to financial deepening in Nigeria. The study concludes that financial deepening has an impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

Macro-economic modeling is generally motivated by two objectives: forecasting and more significantly, policy analysis. In pursuit of these objectives, every model should ideally satisfy four criteria. First, it must fit into a theoretical framework. Second, the specification of the model must reflect a clear understanding of the conceptual framework within which policies are formulated and executed along with an envisaged process of adjustment. Third, it is essential that the model is built on a firm and rich data base and finally, the estimated structural model must adequately utilize the rigors and sophistication of econometric methodology.

Based on the nature of this study, secondary data was used and the design is the ex-post facto. Ex-post facto is a research after the factor has been known and it applies to secondary data (Anyanwu, 2000).

3.2 Theoretical Framework

The theory of financial liberalization pioneered by Mac Kinnon (1973) and Shaw (1973) advocates for the liberalization of the financial sector as an effective way to accelerate growth. The theory suggests that the liberalization of financial markets allows financial deepening which reflects an increasing use of financial intermediation by savers and investors as well as the monetization of the economy. In other words, by lowering financial market frictions, domestic financial savings are increased and foreign capital is attracted. The theory is based on the premise that the higher the real rate of interest, the greater the degree of financial deepening, the more financial saving there will be, and financial saving will be allocated and invested more efficiently than if financial saving is invested directly in the sector in which it takes place, without financial intermediation (Thirlwall 2005). The McKinnon-Shaw theory of financial liberalization suggests a complimentary relationship between the accumulation of money balances (financial assets) and physical capital accumulation in developing countries, leading to economic growth.

3.3 Model Specification

The model for this study is anchored on the theoretical postulations of Mac Kinnon (1973) and Shaw (1973) advocates for the liberalization of the financial sector as an effective way to accelerate growth. The functional form of the model is therefore specified thus;

$$M2/GDP = f(CAPEXP, RECEXP, TAXR, GOVB) \tag{1}$$

The econometric form of the model is therefore specified as thus;

$$M2/GDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CAPEXP_t + \beta_2 RECEXP_t + \beta_3 TAXR_t + \beta_4 GOVB_t + U_t \tag{2}$$

Where:

M2/GDP proxy for financial deepening

CAPEXP– government capital expenditure

RECEXP – government recurrent expenditure

GOVB – government borrowing

TAXR – government tax Revenue

4. RESULTS

4.1 Pre-Estimation Test

Descriptive Statistics

The purpose of the preliminary analysis was to determine the data’s normality, measures of central tendency, and measures of dispersion. The mean and median are central tendency metrics that represent the sample’s average value. The positive square root of variance is standard deviation. It is a measure of dispersion, or the extent to which the deviation from the mean differs from the mean. The Jarque-Bera test’s null hypothesis states that the distribution is normal. We reject the null hypothesis if the probability is less than 0.05.

Table 1. Common Sample Descriptive Statistics

	M2_GDP	TAXR	RECEXP	GOVB	CAPEXP
Maximum	27.37879	9.316217	9.120979	9.864880	7.832993
Minimum	9.063329	2.352203	1.558313	2.415253	1.411011
Std. Dev.	5.972997	2.486790	2.457599	2.249875	2.047642
Skewness	0.510111	-0.557363	-0.392290	-0.312032	-0.593846
Kurtosis	1.585842	1.816852	1.783519	1.894439	1.899357
Jarque-Bera	5.194522	4.514192	3.579628	2.753355	4.479296
Probability	0.074477	0.104654	0.166991	0.252416	0.106496

Source: Researcher’s Extract from Eviews 12 2023. (Please See Appendix)

From Table 1, the result of the descriptive statistics showed that the standard deviation estimate for M2/GDP (financial deepening) was the most volatile in the series with a value of 5.97 while the standard deviation for the regressors i.e lnTAXR, lnRECEXP, lnGOVB and lnCAPEXP were the least volatile variable with a values of 2.48, 2.45, 2,21 and 2.04 respectively. The calculated values for the skewness statistics values of the independent variables were negatively skewed, suggesting that their distributions have a long-left tail while the skewness statistics value for M2/GDP was positively skewed, suggesting that its distribution have a long right tail. Based on these observations, it therefore means that there would be presence of unit root (non-

stationarity) in the series. Thus, estimating these variables at level might not give good results, hence, the need to conduct the unit root test.

Unit Root Test

Table 2. Summary of Stationarity Test Using Augmented Dickey Fuller

Variable	ADF Stat (levels)	5% Critical Value	Prob. Value	ADF. Statistic. 1 st Difference	5% Critical Value	Prob. Value	General Remark
<i>M2/GDP</i>	-1.202537	-2.941145	0.6634	-4.003425*	-2.938987	0.0035	@I(1)
<i>lnCAPEXP</i>	-1.547585	-2.936942	0.4996	-8.409713*	-2.938987	0.0000	@I(1)
<i>lnRECEXP</i>	-1.766695	-2.941145	0.8174	-10.35897*	-2.938987	0.0000	@I(1)
<i>LnGOVB</i>	-2.187699	-2.941145	0.0622	-9.184150*	-2.938987	0.0000	@I(1)
<i>lnTAXR</i>	-2.357403	-2.945842	0.1606	-7.974075*	-2.938987	0.0000	@I(1)

Source: Researcher’s Compilation from Eviews 12 Regression Output

The asterisks(*) sign is used to indicate stationarity at the 5% significance level

The result of the unit root test in table 2, indicated that all the variables i.e lnM2/GDP, lnCAPEXP, lnRECEXP, lnGOVB and lnTAXR achieved stationarity at first differences I(1), justifying the chosen estimation technique which is the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) with can be able to accommodate the introduction of the Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) in order to determine the convergence of the variables in the long run.

Cointegration Test

Table 3. Johansen Cointegration Test

Series:		M2_GDP		
lnCAPEXP lnRECEXP lnGOVB lnTAXR				
Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 2				
Hypothesized	Trace	0.05		
		Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.593110	77.34322	69.81889	0.0111
At most 1	0.426509	43.17310	47.85613	0.1284
At most 2	0.316515	22.04462	29.79707	0.2960
At most 3	0.144764	7.583720	15.49471	0.5109
At most 4	0.042274	1.641351	3.841465	0.2001

Source: Researcher’s Extract from Eviews 12 Software Package

Based on the cointegration result from table 3, trace test indicated one cointegrating equations at the 0.05 level of significance, implying rejection of the null hypothesis of no cointegration at the 0.05 level of significance and we conclude that there exists a long relationship among the dependent and explanatory variables.

Dynamic Short Run Error Correction Model**Table 4: Dynamic Error Correction Term Estimates****Dependent Variable: M2/GDP**

Method: Least Squares

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
<i>C</i>	3.475209	2.388922	1.454718	0.1549
<i>lnCAPEXP</i>	-2.118495	0.922296	-2.296980	0.0279
<i>lnRECEXP</i>	2.913905	1.666335	1.748691	0.0894
<i>lnGOVB</i>	3.314753	1.274716	2.600386	0.0137
<i>lnTAXR</i>	-2.234762	1.135140	-1.968710	0.0572
<i>RESID01(-1)</i>	-0.704895	0.123282	5.717751	0.0000
R-squared	0.884788	Mean dependent var		16.72919
F-statistic	52.22176	Durbin-Watson stat		1.603611
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Researcher's Compilation from Eviews 12.

From the short run error correction term regression result in table 4, the value of the constant term (*C*) was positively signed with a value of 3.475209 units, this implies that when the regressors *lnCAPEXP*, *lnRECEXP*, *lnRECEXP*, *lnGOVB*, *lnTAXR* are held constant, financial deepening (M2/GDP) in Nigeria will increase by 3.475209 units on the average.

Capital Expenditure in Nigeria (*lnCAPEXP*): Analysis of the short run coefficient of capital expenditure was negatively signed with a value of -2.118495 and statistically significant at 5% level of significance, implying a negative relationship with financial deepening in Nigeria, whereby a 1% change in capital expenditure will decrease the value of M2/GDP by 2.118495 units on the average.

Recurrent Expenditure in Nigeria (*lnRECEXP*): Analysis of the short run coefficient of recurrent expenditure was positively signed with a value of 2.913905 and statistically insignificant at 5% level of significance, implying a positive relationship with financial deepening in Nigeria, whereby a 1% change in recurrent expenditure increase the value of M2/GDP by 2.913905 units, insignificantly on the average.

Government Borrowing (*lnGOVB*): Analysis of the short run coefficient of government borrowing was positively signed with a value of 3.314753 and statistically significant at 5% level of significance, implying a positive relationship with financial deepening in Nigeria, whereby a 1% change in government borrowing will increase the value of M2/GDP by 3.314753 units on the average.

Taxation Revenue in Nigeria (*TAXR*): Analysis of the short run coefficient of taxation revenue was negatively signed with a value of -2.234762 and statistically insignificant at 5% level of significance, implying a negative relationship with financial deepening in Nigeria, whereby a 1% change in taxation revenue will decrease the value of M2/GDP by 2.234762 units, insignificantly on the average

RESID(-1)The significance and rule of Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) holds that negative and statistical significant error correction coefficients are necessary conditions for any

disequilibrium to be corrected. In light of this, the coefficient of RESID(-1) is -0.704895. The above result showed that the RESID(-1) value is -0.70% implying that there is a convergence of the equilibrium should there be system disequilibrium. The negative sign of the coefficient satisfied one condition while the fact that its P-value [0.0000] is less than 5% [0.05] level of significance satisfied the second condition of statistical significance. The coefficient indicates that the speed of adjustment between the short run dynamics and the long run equilibrium is 70%. Thus, the error correction mechanism will adequately act to correct any deviations of the short run dynamics to its long-run equilibrium by 70% annually, implying that if financial deepening (M2/GDP) is at disequilibrium, it converges back to equilibrium at an average speed of about 70% every year in Nigeria.

R-Squared: R-squared of 0.884788 indicated that 88% of the total variation in financial deepening (M2/GDP) is averagely accounted for by Capital Expenditure (lnCAPEXP), Recurrent Expenditure (lnRECEXP), Taxation Revenue (TAXR), Government Borrowing (lnGOVB) However, the total variation of 12% in M2/GDP is attributable to the influence of other factors not included in the regression model.

Diagnostic Test/Post Estimation Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test

The standard errors and variances of the variables estimated in the model are affected by serial correlation in the error term, confounding inference. The study used a serial correlation LM check for autocorrelation in the error term entering the model to prevent this problem. The test's outcome is shown in the table below.

Table 5. Result Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:			
F-statistic	1.814554	Prob. F(2,13)	0.7655
Obs*R-squared	4.074317	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.1304

Source: Researcher's Extract from Eviews 12 Output package.

From Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test table, the null hypothesis of no serial correlation cannot be rejected as the p-value from the LM serial correlation test is 0.1304 > 0.05 level of significance indicating an acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity is when the ordinary least squares rule is broken. The error terms' variance is homoscedastic, which means they have a constant variance, according to the regression assumption. Simply defined, heteroskedasticity occurs when the error terms' variance is not constant across all X values. The study used a Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test in the error term entering the model to prevent this issue. The test's outcome is shown in the table below.

Table 6. Result of Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey			
F-statistic	0.193015	Prob. F(20,14)	0.9995
Obs*R-squared	7.564865	Prob. Chi-Square(20)	0.9149

Source: Researcher's Extract from Eviews 12 Output package.

From Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity result, the null hypothesis of no serial correlation cannot be rejected as the p-value from the Heteroskedasticity Test is $0.9149 > 0.05$ level of significance indicating an acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Stability Test

Ramsey Reset Test

The Ramsey Regression Equation Specification Error Test (RESET) is a general linear regression model specification test. It examines if non-linear combinations of the fitted values aid in the explanation of the response variable.

Table 7. Result of Ramsey Reset Test

Ramsey RESET Test			
Specification: $\ln M2/GDP, CAPEXP, RECEXP, GOVB TAXR ECT(-1) C$			
t-statistic	1.437323	33	0.1600
F-statistic	2.065896	(1, 33)	0.1600
Likelihood ratio	2.428859	1	0.1191

Source: Researcher’s Extract from Eviews 12 Output package.

From the RESET test result, the null hypothesis of no specification error cannot be rejected as the p-value from the RESET F-test is $0.6100 > 0.05$ level of significance indicating an acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Cumulative and Cumulative Squares Test

The cusum and cusum of squares for model stability was employed to check for the stability of the parameters in the model. The result of the stability test is shown below:

Figure 1. Cusum test for model stability

Figure 2. Cusum of Squares for model stability

The cusum and cusum squares diagrams shows that the model is stable as the cusum line lies in between the 5% boundary.

4.2 Discussion of Findings

Effect of capital expenditure on financial deepening in Nigeria.

Analysis of the short run coefficient of capital expenditure had a negative and significant effect and relationship with financial deepening in Nigeria at 0.05 level of significance. This finding did not conform to the apriori expectation because most capital expenditure components enter into productive projects like bridges, roads, schools, airports, hospitals, among others, which have higher social benefits and longer paybacks - serving as a positive externality to economic activities in the economy.

Recurrent Expenditure in Nigeria (lnRECEXP): Analysis of the short run coefficient of recurrent expenditure had a positive and insignificant relationship with financial deepening in Nigeria at 5% level of significance. This may be connected with the fact that significant portion of recurrent expenditure in Nigeria goes to payment of debt servicing during the study period. Large scale corruption in the country which allows the easy conversion of recurrent expenditure into private public office holders' accounts through the use of ghost workers, bogus budgets and expenditures and other illegal practices could be responsible for the insignificant effect on financial deepening in Nigeria.

Government Borrowing (lnGOVB): Analysis of the short run coefficient of government borrowing had a positive and significant relationship with financial deepening in Nigeria 5% level of significance. This finding is not far-fetched since Government borrowing is of economic significance in several other respects. First, the buying and selling of government securities provides the central bank with a means of influencing the money supply, essential for effective monetary policy. Second, borrowing avoids the adverse effects that taxes may have on incentives, particularly if the taxes are raised sharply above levels to which persons have become accustomed. Third, borrowing permits government expenditures to be higher than would otherwise be feasible. Finally, the foreign borrowing of some governments gives them access to a greater quantity of foreign exchange, which enables them to finance the import of capital goods essential for economic growth

Taxation Revenue in Nigeria (TAXR): Analysis of the short run coefficient of taxation revenue had a negative and insignificant relationship with financial deepening in Nigeria at 5% level of significance. This finding did not follow apriori expectation of the model because tax revenue is an avenue for the government to source for funds to use and improve the workings of the economy and this would lead to economic growth by increasing the money supply. The findings from the study supported the Laffer curve theory. The Laffer curve theory simply revealed that any change in tax rate will have economic effect in areas of work, output, employment, and in consequence the tax base by contributing to expand the activities through incentives. The findings from the study also supported the endogenous growth model which explained that economic growth is influenced by internal factors rather than external factors. Tax was one of the internal factors as it is generated internally through the workings of human capital.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

This study used the OLS estimation technique with the help of the Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) to investigate effect of fiscal policy instruments on financial deepening in Nigeria for the period 1981-2022. From our findings, government borrowing is a major determinant of financial deepening in Nigeria with recurrent expenditure even though its effect was insignificant.

Capital expenditure and tax revenue contributed negatively to financial deepening in Nigeria. The conclusion to be drawn from this study is that capital expenditure, recurrent expenditure and tax revenue are poor contributors to financial deepening in Nigeria in the presence of other internal and external macro-economic shocks. Nevertheless, to achieve a high and sustainable growth, we proffer some policy recommendations which when properly implemented will surely stimulate greater growth of output. We recommend as follows:

1. In order to adequately harness the expected returns of public capital spending in the economy, the Nigerian government has to be decisive and more transparent in its fight against financial corruption and diversion of public funds especially those that are allocated for the execution of capital projects across the country.
2. Government in Nigeria should increase its expenditure on highway projects as this will provide the needed infrastructure that can enhance the private sector productivity, easy distribution of raw and finished goods and enhance economic growth and also expand its spending share of capital expenditure to further enhance the growth of the economy, since it has been getting small share as compared to recurrent expenditure. To ensure higher productivity of capital in promoting economic growth, capital allocations should be prioritized based on projects and areas that have strong benefits to the citizens and sound linkages with various sectors of the economy
3. The negative relationship between tax revenue and financial deepening calls for efficient tax policy to be formulated and implemented so as it to continue to generate the needed revenue for the government. Also revenue collecting authorities of the government should be made more effective in their operations of collecting revenue for the government. Equally important is the need for the upgrading of revenue collecting technique so as to be able to generate more tax revenue for the government.
4. The Nigerian government should try as much as possible to raise her borrowings from sources within the country (internal borrowing), so as to limit the foreign debt effect arising from foreign exchange risk since repayment (interest and principal) will be in foreign currency which often impact on the interest rate. In addition, the Nation should ensure a prudent debt management policy that would ensure that borrowings are only made to finance top priority projects.
5. Government should equitably distribute its income spending between recurrent spending and capital expenditure in such a way that there should be no much significant difference.

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